

The Effects of Corona Virus Disease (COVID-19) on Restaurant Marketing Strategies of Café Restaurant around San Pedro, Laguna

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Abstract: The ultimate aim of this study is to know how the café owners overcome the challenges they've been through when the pandemic hit the country and what marketing strategies they used, to rise up again while experiencing pandemic. With this study, we will know how they manage to continue with their businesses and what platforms they use to advertise or promote their café businesses that will be beneficial not just for the BSHM students but also to all the people that have their own café business. This study starts by knowing the effects of COVID-19 on café businesses and their restaurant marketing strategies and their demographic profile. Also, how this pandemic affects their strategy especially since people cannot go outside or cannot dine in due to health protocols set by the government. Lastly finalized the data by creating a survey questionnaire and generating a tabulation of all the data collected from the respondents. An online survey in the form of google forms was used for the methodology to gather data from 30 business owners who voluntarily take the survey. Results indicated that the majority of the business owners who had their café business affected by the pandemic are women and people in the range of 26 - 35 years old. A detailed critical analysis of the results is provided in the last chapter.

Keywords: Corona Virus Disease (COVID-19), Restaurant Marketing Strategies, Café Restaurant.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the past couple of years, restaurant marketing strategies have become even more nuanced. Those in charge of promotions and creating new restaurant business are facing challenging and fascinating challenges. There is now a dizzying array of potential choices for people looking to fill their stomachs, and restaurants must fight for customer attention beyond venue. Because of these different kinds of marketing strategies was planned and implemented by the people who are assigned to it. A marketing strategy refers to the methods you implement to promote your products and services to your target audience. It can include website content, television and radio advertising, and content launched on social media platforms. In the Philippines the restaurants are already recovering through the marketing plans that they are conducting which we can mostly see in social media. According to the website Statista.com (2020), the sales revenue is expected to show an annual growth rate (CAGR 2020-2025) of 17.8%, resulting in a projected market volume of US\$461m by 2025. On of the place that has been affected by the pandemic, and in this study the researchers will see how marketing strategies help them to recover with the situation.

Developing an effective marketing strategy for your business is the key to growth, expansion, and long-term success. The challenge, however, is that developing the right marketing strategy can involve a lot of hit or miss, and for small businesses, the costs related to misunderstanding your market can be catastrophic. (S. Quain, 2019). Marketing strategy is not only about improving leads and turning them into customers, but also about sharing the company's culture, values, and purpose.

The essence of branding is the process of communicating your vision to your audience. This will help you to know what your customers' needs and wants, it will help you to improve your products and services. But this is also a risk that the business or the business owners are taking, it is because of the costs of marketing. Because according to S. Quain (2019), Although the digital revolution has somewhat evened the playing field, the truth is that small business is still at a disadvantage, when it comes to grabbing their share of eyeballs through their marketing efforts. Big data has great value, but accessing that data is expensive, and you have to keep analyzing that data to stay abreast of buyer trends. Launching a marketing campaign on your website can also be expensive, especially if you're using a pay-per-click strategy to attract more prospects. Television and radio advertising spots are also costly, and even local advertising space is at a premium, because there is so much competition for the local audience. Also, he stated that the time and effort for the marketing strategy may not yield. Big brands can afford to spend time and effort working on a marketing campaign that fails, because they have the resources to regroup and move on. As a small business owner, however, the return on investment on a marketing campaign may be low, and that means you have spent months crafting a strategy that did nothing to help your bottom line. Even the most well-planned marketing campaigns fail, and at the small business level, that can set you back for months.

Since January 2020, when the World Health Organization (WHO) declared that the new corona virus disease (Covid-19) is a public health emergency of international concern, all dimensions of life have experienced risks and opportunities. Like other industries, the food and beverage industry has been hit hard by impacts from the COVID-19 pandemic, which has caused enormous losses in many sectors of the global economy. One of the industrial sectors that had to overcome different challenges during the pandemic is the food sector, striving to produce and secure sufficient and safe food. This global effect of the corona virus has led to unprecedented economic and public health concerns, which will likely transform how businesses operate going forward. This transformation will be limited not only to how businesses operate but also to how they sustain and grow their brand and customer base. Central to this concern is how businesses attract consumers and promote their products and services.

To determine the different marketing strategies, the researchers will make use of the 4 Ps (product, price, place, promotion) also known as marketing mix, these are contained with internal and external factors in the overall business environment, which interacts with one another. As the business world already shifted to being indoors and having everything be less people to people interaction, the researcher would like to see the effects of the pandemic to the marketing strategies of cafe restaurants that had opened and trying to get back up in these trying times.

The COVID-19 epidemic is a sharp warning that pandemics have occurred in the past and will continue to occur in the future, like other rarely occurring disasters. We should intend to lessen their effects on society even though we are unable to prevent the creation of dangerous viruses. Throughout the globe, the latest epidemic has had serious economic effects, and it does not look like any nation would be unaffected. The coronavirus epidemic has prompted businesses to re-evaluate how contact centers are utilized, how workers provide valuable customer services, where they operate, and how digital platforms can be used during the crisis and beyond to promote business stability.

The significance of this study is to help the people in the business industry to know what kind of marketing strategy that will allow the business to be recognize by the people or the target market. This study will be a guideline for the business owners to prepare a marketing plan that will be conducted specially when they experience this kind of situation.

Research Paradigm

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 depicts the Input Process Output (IPO) model. The researcher used IPO model because it offers an efficient way to both analyses and document the crucial aspects of a transformation process. An input process output is simply a way to describe how your business processes information. The input consists of the variables such as demographic profile of the respondents in terms of Age, gender, years in business and monthly sales to the concept of effect of Corona Virus Disease on restaurants marketing strategies.

The process involves conducting a survey among the participants through an online survey questionnaire. The last is the perception of respondent on the analysis of Corona virus on restaurants marketing strategy which will serve as the output of the study.

Statement of the Problem

The study aims to determine or to assess the effect of corona virus disease on marketing strategies of Cafe Restaurants around San Pedro, Laguna specifically this will answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Gender
 - 1.3 Years in business
 - 1.4 Monthly sales
2. How does the respondents assess The Effect of Corona Virus Disease on Restaurant Marketing Strategies in terms of:
 - 2.1 Price
 - 2.2 Product
 - 2.3 Promotion
 - 2.4 Place
3. Is there a significant difference in the ASSESSMENT of the respondents ON THE **The Effect of Corona Virus Disease (COVID-19) on Restaurant Marketing Strategies of Café Restaurant around San Pedro, Laguna** in terms of:
 - a.Price.
 - b.Product
 - c.Promotion
 - d.Place
- 4.Is there a significant relationship between the assessment on the effect of Corona Virus Disease(COVID-19) on the Restaurant Marketing Strategies of the owners of Café Restaurant in San Pedro, Laguna and their demographic characteristics?
4. Based on the analysis and results of the study, what recommendations can be proposed?

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Impact of Pandemic

Donthu and Gustafsson (2020) The COVID-19 outbreak is a sharp reminder that pandemics, like other rarely occurring catastrophes, have happened in the past and will continue to happen in the future. Even if we cannot prevent dangerous viruses from emerging, we should prepare to dampen their effects on society. The current outbreak has had severe economic consequences across the globe, and it does not look like any country will be unaffected. This not only has consequences for the economy; all of society is affected, which has led to dramatic changes in how businesses act and consumers behave.

Effects of Covid/What is covid?

Kandola (2021) Viruses work by hijacking cells. They enter host cells and reproduce, then spread to new cells throughout the body. Coronaviruses are large, single-stranded Trusted Source RNA viruses with crown-like protein spikes on their

surfaces. Once inside the body, they mostly affect the respiratory system, including the nose and lungs. This can cause inflammation and other effects. Coronaviruses spread among people through droplets from coughs, sneezes, or breathing.

Regarding 4P's

Kat Barber (2020) The 4Ps of marketing is a simple way of thinking about marketing plans across four main areas: product, price, place, and promotion. It's important to always put the customers' needs at the center of your marketing plans. This will ensure you are always delivering a product they actually want, not what your company wants. This study aims to learn the process and plans of the said restaurants and on how they adapted to the environment amidst the challenging times of the pandemic.

Jeff Raymond (2022) A deliberate review of the 4Ps of marketing in the context of this temporary new normal is a helpful construct to ensure your marketing strategy remains on the best possible course. The 4Cs (chaos, calamity, confusion, and complexity.) include understanding and adjusting to customers' needs and pain points, finding creative solutions and meeting them where they are with messages that show "we know what you are going through and we are here to help". This study aims to know how the 4Ps are being applied in the café restaurants in San Pedro, Laguna. MORE

Shinozaki and Nagraj Rao (2021) The strict lockdown ran from mid-March to the end of May 2020 in the national capital region and high-risk provinces. Micro, small, and medium-sized enterprises (MSMEs) are continuing to confront a sharp drop in demand and revenue. Six months after the March lockdown, the Philippine economy has moved to the recovery stage, but micro, small, and medium-sized enterprises (MSMEs) are continuing to confront a sharp drop in demand and revenue. The café restaurants around San Pedro Laguna are heavily affected by these changes since there are a lot of restaurants of the same category in the area affected.

Nuestro (2020) The first hurdle that most owners, if not all, faced when the Enhanced Community Quarantine (ECQ) had started is how to sustain the livelihood of their employees. An estimate of over half a million employees in the F&B sector are now greatly affected and receive no income. This study aims to learn on how these café restaurants address the new normal.

Vigilia et.al (2020) One of the worst-hit sectors is the restaurant industry. Covid-19 has caused problems worldwide, not just in the Philippines but the whole world. Several of the establishments were about to close. Nevertheless, only few businesses managed to survive operations. As consistently reported and verified, In February and March 2020, COVID-19 instances skyrocketed, according to more restaurant owners reported fewer sales as compared to the same period in the preceding years and in 2019.

Cromwell et.al (2020) stated that the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the restaurant and hospitality industries has been unprecedented in its breadth and severity. A number of publicly traded restaurant companies have withdrawn earnings guidance in the last week until they have more clarity on the pandemic. Small businesses within these industries face even greater uncertainty. Since majority of the café restaurants around San Pedro, Laguna are small businesses and the article said that these small businesses face even greater uncertainty, therefore this study aims to find the impact of the pandemic towards the café restaurants.

T. Baltic et.al (2021) Since 2020, the SARS-CoV-2 virus has spread quickly over the world, causing the COVID-19 pandemic, which has had enormous influence on people's health, economies, and societies. Due to the infection's quick spread among humans, the situation needed to be quickly adjusted to in order to safeguard public health and limit financial damages. All parties involved in the situation must work to stop new outbreaks and reduce associated dangers because the current epidemic has resulted in reported cases in the millions. Every participant in the food supply chain is referred to as the "food sector" in this context. This study highlights the industry's response to the pandemic problem while also examining the challenges faced by the entire food supply chain.

Nhamo, Dube, & Chikodzi (2020) One of the top global employers and a significant source of income is the hospitality sector, particularly the restaurant sector. However, the sector is vulnerable to natural calamities, particularly the emergence of pandemics and epidemics, which disrupt infrastructure and impair human movement. In this study, the early effects of COVID-19 on the world's restaurants were examined.

Effects of Corona Virus to the Business Industry

According to Emely Wright (2020) Corona virus offers the opportunity to look and understand business strategy in a new light, as perhaps never has the entire business environment changed so rapidly as a result of one universal problem. While

financial crises are often widespread, they affect some businesses more than others, and often hold resemblances to historical crises, aiding businesses' response strategy. COVID-19 is completely different to anything in modern history, hence meaning the modern corporation will have no previous experience on how to tackle it. The one thing that is certain about strategy is that it is needed for business survival, and therefore is most definitely at the centre of all businesses right now. Perhaps normally, strategy is a slow-moving process, as the external environment slowly changes at the pace of new technologies. However, this case is completely different. On the 20th March 2020, the Prime Minister announced the closure of cafes, pubs, restaurants, night clubs, theatres, gyms and many other businesses. This meant as quickly as the Prime Minister could give the instruction "close tonight... not to open tomorrow" strategy must be in the process of changing. This fast rate of change of strategy on such a wide scale may give us a better insight into pinpointing the exact effect of Corona virus is on the strategy of small businesses.

COVID 19 and the Economy

COVID-19 is not only a global pandemic and public health crisis. The global economy and financial markets have also been seriously impacted by it. Large income declines, increasing unemployment and disturbances in the transport, utility and manufacturing sectors are among the implications of the disease control measures introduced in many countries.

On March 11, 2020, the World Health Organization (WHO) characterized COVID-19 as a pandemic, pointing to over 3 million cases and 207,973 deaths in 213 countries and territories. The infection has not only become a public health crisis but has also affected the global economy. Significant economic impact has already occurred across the globe due to reduced productivity, loss of life, business closures, trade disruption, and decimation of the tourism industry. COVID-19 may be that a "wake-up" call for global leaders to intensify cooperation on epidemic preparedness and provide the necessary financing for international collective action. (Geneva, 2020). There has been ample information on the expected economic and health costs of infectious disease outbreaks, but the world has failed to adequately invest in preventive and preparedness measures to mitigate the risks of large epidemics. (Yamey G, Schäferhoff M, Aars OK, Bloom B, Carroll D, Chawla M, et al, 2017).

Marketing Strategy

It was stated by A. Borone (2020), that marketing strategy is a overall game plan for reaching prospective consumers and turning them into customers of the products or services the business provides. A marketing strategy contains the company's value proposition, key brand messaging, data on target customer demographics, and other high-level elements.

This is important because a business without a marketing strategy will not be successful in the future because it will not be seen by the people. It is necessary that the marketing strategy that a business will perform is well planned because it will have a big impact to the business or the company.

Marketing strategy is an essential factor to have a successful business. This will allow them to have an interaction with their target market or audience. that will help them to grow the business in the future.

Marketing Plan

S. Mcguire (2020), A marketing plan will be a report that outlines your marketing strategy for the coming year, quarter or month. This includes An overview of your business's marketing and advertising goals, a description of your business's current marketing position, a timeline of when tasks within your strategy will be completed, key performance indicators (KPIs) you will be tracking, a description of your business's target market and customer needs. Learning how to write a marketing plan forces you to think through the important steps that lead to an effective marketing strategy and a well-defined plan will help you stay focused on your high-level marketing goals.

Marketing

Professionals who work in a corporation's marketing and promotion departments seek to get the attention of key potential audiences through advertising. Promotions are targeted to certain audiences and may involve celebrity endorsements, catchy phrases or slogans, memorable packaging or graphic designs and overall media exposure.

Marketing undertakes to promote the buying or selling of a product or service. Marketing includes advertising, selling, and delivering products to consumers or other businesses. Some marketing is done by affiliates on behalf of a company.

Internal and External Marketing

It was stated on the website Visagievos (2020), Internal marketing refers to the process of motivating and empowering employees to work as a team for the overall wellbeing of the company and consequently, the clients. A synchronized effort within the company is essential to providing clients with services at the desired level. The interaction of employees with clients mostly influences service quality and client satisfaction to such an extent that it has become important for companies to focus on ways to influence and manage these interactions. It also refers to the partnership or communication between management and employees. The employees need to form part of the company's vision, to know what is expected of them. If the vision is clear, employees are provided with the opportunity to learn and enhance and should be rewarded accordingly. This can be done by means of recognition, benefits, salary increase, team building activities etc. The appropriate funding should be allocated to keep internal clients satisfied, so staff retention will not decrease.

External marketing is the action of promoting and selling services or products, which includes market research and advertising to clients and potential clients. In service industries, employees represent their company to clients through their interactions with them, and therefore these interactions must be positive, so clients will keep coming back. It thus refers to the relationship between the company and its clients. The aim should always be to increase the clients' experience. The retention of clients is of vital importance. Effort should be made to gather feedback on clients' satisfaction and this feedback should be used to improve internal systems.

4 Ps (Product, Price, Place, Promotion)

According to Alexandra Twin, The four Ps of marketing are the key factors that are involved in the marketing of a good or service. The 4 Ps are used by companies to identify some key factors for their business, including what consumers want from them, how their product or service meets or fails to meet those needs, how their product or service is perceived in the world, how they stand out from their competitors, and how they interact with their customers. The 4Ps is a simple way of thinking about marketing plans across four main areas: Product, Price, Place and Promotion. This will help formulate a plan to ensure the introduction of a product or service. The Product defines what exactly the product/service you are offering is, and what benefit it will give to customers. And the Price is how much will the product be sold for, and how this compares to competitors in the market. The next one is the Promotion, when, where and how you will advertise your product to ensure it reaches your target audience. Lastly is the Place, where will customers go learn about and purchase your product. This covers sales outlets and e-commerce markets.

3. METHODOLOGY

This part of the study presents the methods that will be used in the study which are the sampling method, research design, data gathering procedures and more that will be used to determine the effect of corona virus in the café restaurant marketing strategies.

Research Design

The Researcher uses Quantitative research because this method emphasizes objective measurements and the statistical, mathematical, or numerical analysis of data collected through online survey questionnaires. The researcher will use quantitative research to obtain information that will help in making a generalization about a population under study.

Sampling Method

In this study, the researcher will be using purposive sampling method in choosing the respondents. Purposive sampling method is a technique that uses an expert's judgment in the collection of cases or chooses cases for a specific reason. This will be used to prevent getting information that is not correlated or irrelevant to the study.

Research locale

The study will be conducted in 30 selected restaurants within the area of San Pedro, Laguna. The researchers have chosen this area since this is more practical and accessible in times of pandemic since San Pedro, Laguna has a considerable number of Cafés and Restaurants.

Research participants

In this study, the researcher ensures that the respondents would understand the nature of instrument, they set up qualifications to know if the chosen respondents are qualified to provide information's with regards the topic.

The respondents will be composed of thirty (30) restaurant owners whose business is located in San Pedro, Laguna as respondents.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher will use survey questionnaire as their main instrument of the study. This survey questionnaire will be answered by the respondents through social media, specifically google forms. The survey was divided into 4 parts. The first part consists of the questions about the products of the restaurants. Second part consists of the questions how the pandemic affects the price of the product. Third part consists of the questions how it affects the promotion of the restaurant. The fourth part consists of the questions how the location of the business affects the distribution of the products.

The internal consistency and the reliability of the instrument was tested using the Cronbach alpha test. Ten participants were initially used in the test and this yielded an alpha value of 0.75 which is interpreted as good and acceptable. (See Reliability test results in the appendices.)

Research instruments

The researcher will use Survey Questionnaire as the main instrument for this study. And they will be using a rating scale called Likert scale, a Likert scale is a unidimensional scale that researchers use to collect respondents’ attitudes and opinions. Researchers often use this psychometric scale to understand the views and perspectives towards a brand, product, or target market (Dan Fleetwood, 2020). This will be use so that the researchers can operationalize the data and information’s that they have gathered can be analyzed quantitatively.

Data treatment and analysis

The researcher will use descriptive statistics to present the data that will be gathered using the online survey questionnaire. This will be used as the data treatment to simplify large amounts of data in a more sensible way. And for the data analysis, the researcher will use coding, clustering and data transcription. In order to find the connection between the collected data from the interviewees, researcher can analyze the data by coding information. The percentage method will be used in the analysis of the demographic profile of the participants. The weighted mean is used in the assessment of the effects of Covid-19 on the marketing strategies of the café restaurant owners. For inferential statistics, the researchers will use ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) to compute or test the significance of difference on the effects of Covid 19 virus to the café restaurant marketing strategies in terms of the 4Ps. The null hypothesis will be tested at .05 level of significance. The chi square test of association is used in determining the significance of the relationship between the assessment on the effects of Covid-19 on the marketing strategies of the owners of café restaurants in San Pedro, Laguna and their demographic profiles.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the results of the study conducted and their discussion.

Table 1: Age Profile of Participants

AGE	F(N=30)	P
BELOW 18	0	0%
18-25	6	19.98
26-35	10	33.3
36-45	8	26.64
ABOVE 45	6	19.98

shows the age distribution of the participants in this study. Most of the participants are within the age range of 26 to 35 years old. This is followed by those whose ages are 36-45 years old. The participants with ages of 18-25 years old and those above 45 years old are at 19.98% of the total number of participants. There are no participants below 18 years old.

These findings imply that most café restaurant owners in San Pedro, Laguna are still young and may be assumed to be flexible in making important management decisions in their businesses.

Table 2: Gender Profile of the Participants

GENDER	F(N=30)	P
MALE	13	43.29%
FEMALE	17	56.61

The table shows the gender profile of the participants in the study. More than half of them is female at 56.61% while the males comprise 43.29%. This implies that café restaurant owners in San Pedro are mostly managed by women. There are certain differences in the marketing strategies between men and women. For men, concrete information and data carries more weight while for women, comprehensive data combined with emotional connections, seem to give the best results.

Table 3: Years in Business Profile

YEARS	F(N=30)	P
BELOW 2	4	13.32%
2-4	8	26.64
4-6	10	33.3
ABOVE 6	8	26.64

In terms of years in the business, most of the participants are in the restaurant business for 4 to 6 years already. This is followed by those who have been in the business for 2-4 years and those with more than 6 years. Only 13.32% of the participants are in the business below two years.

These imply that the owners of café restaurant in San Pedro are well-experienced in handling restaurant operations given their number of years in the business.

Table 4: Effects of COVID-19 Pandemic to Marketing Strategies Product

In terms of strategies with respect to product, the participants say that Covid-19 has a high negative effect with a mean of 2.58. They disagree on the following indicators: the popularity of their products during the pandemic; the products being saleable during the pandemic; the availability of the products; and that the products were not affected by the pandemic. The lowest mean of disagreement is seen in the availability of the products. However, the participants are neutral when it comes to the products being trendy and appealing during the pandemic.

AREAS	MEAN	INTERPRETATION
1.PRODUCT		
1.1 The products during this pandemic are still popular.	2.60	DISAGREE(D)
1.2 The products are still saleable even in this time of pandemic.	2.57	D
1.3 All of the food products are available.	2.47	D
1.4 The food products are still trendy and appealing to our customers.	2.77	NEUTRAL(N)
1.5 The food products were not affected by the pandemic.	2.50	D
MEAN	2.58	HIGH NEGATIVE EFFECT

Price

With regards to strategies regarding price, the participants see that the pandemic brought high negative effect also. They show disagreement to all the indicators under this area. These are: affordability of the food prices; that the food prices remained constant in the time of the pandemic; that the food prices blend well with the product value; that the food prices were not affected by the pandemic; and that the affordability and the quality of the products give satisfaction to the customers. The lowest mean of disagreement is seen in the affordability of the food prices.

2.PRICE		
2.1 The food prices are still affordable.	2.40	D
2.2 Our food prices are still the same even in this time of pandemic.	2.6	D
2.3 The food prices blend well with the product value.	2.43	D
2.4 The food prices were not affected by the pandemic.	2.57	D
2.5 The affordability and quality of the food products gives satisfaction to the customers.	2.43	D
MEAN	2.49	HIGH NEGATIVE EFFECT

Promotion

Moderate negative effect of the pandemic is seen by the participants when it comes to promotion. They showed neutrality on the following indicators: the big part played by social media in promotion; the difficulty in promoting the business during the pandemic; the frequent promotions made; and that online promotion helped to boost sales. The lowest mean of neutrality is manifested in the part played by social media in promotion. On the other hand, the participants agree that they used offline/online marketing strategies for promotion during the pandemic.

3.PROMOTIONS		
3.1 Social media has a huge part when it comes to promotion.	3.03	N
3.2 Promoting the business is difficult during the pandemic	3.10	N
3.3 Promotion of business is frequent.	3.23	N
3.4 Used any offline/online marketing strategies for promotion.	3.70	AGREE(A)
3.5 Online promotion has helped boost sales during the pandemic.	3.47	N
MEAN	3.31	MODERATE NEGATIVE EFFECT

Place

For the participants, the pandemic produced slight negative effect in terms of place. They agree that the current place of their establishment is highly accessible and Covid-19 has not lessened the flow of customers with the highest mean of agreement. Neutrality is seen in the current place of the business has no adverse effects on sales; the pandemic has not lessened customers density; and the adoption of measures against Covid for the safety of the customers.

4.PLACE		
4.1 Current place of the establishment is very accessible.	3.63	A
4.2 Current place of the establishment has no adverse effects on sales.	3.30	N
4.3 COVID-19 has affected the density customers visiting.	3.57	N
4.4 COVID-19 lessened the flow of customers.	3.70	A
4.5 Establishment has adapted precautionary measures for COVID-19 for the safety of the place and its customers.	3.20	N
MEAN	3.48	SLIGHT NEGATIVE EFFECT

LEGEND:

MEAN RANGE INTERPRETATION

1.00-1.80 STRONGLY DISAGREE/VERY HIGH NEGATIVE EFFECT

1.81-2.60 DISAGREE/HIGH NEGATIVE EFFECT

2.61-3.40 NEUTRAL/MODERATE NEGATIVE EFFECT

3.41-4.20 AGREE/SLIGHT NEGATIVE EFFECT

4.21-5.00 STRONGLY AGREE/NO NEGATIVE EFFECT AT ALL

Table 4 gives the assessment of the participants on the effects of Covid-19 on their marketing strategies namely: product, price, promotion, and place.

Place

For the participants, the pandemic produced slight negative effect in terms of place. They agree that the current place of their establishment is highly accessible and Covid-19 has not lessened the flow of customers with the highest mean of agreement. Neutrality is seen in the current place of the business has no adverse effects on sales; the pandemic has not lessened customers density; and the adoption of measures against Covid for the safety of the customers.

Table 5: ANOVA Test Results on the Significant Difference between Product, Price, Promotions, and Place.

SOURCE OF VARIATION	SS	DF	MS	F	P-VALUE	F CRIT
BETWEEN GROUPS	3.79	3	1.26	34.5	.000	3.24
WITHIN GROUPS	0.59	16	0.04			
TOTAL	4.38	19				

In determining the significance of the differences in the assessment made on the effects of Covid-19 on marketing strategies in terms of product, price, promotion, and place, the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) is used. The test done at .05 significance level is used to determine if the differences in the assessment made are significant between and within groups. The key figures that must be looked upon in the table are the F critical value and the p-value. It is seen in the table that the value of F which is 34.5 is greater than the critical value of 3.24. Hence, the differences are significant. The other figure is the p-value which is .000 which is less than the .05 level of significance. This means that the differences in the means of product, price, promotion, and place are significant or they are too great to be ignored. As given in the table 4, slight negative effect is seen in place; moderate in promotion; and high in product and place. This accounts for the significance in their mean differences. This implies that the effects of Covid-19 vary in terms of the strategies implemented in product, price, promotion, and place.

Table 6: CHI Square Test Results on the Significance of Relationship Between Effects of COVID-19 on the Marketing Strategies of Café Restaurant Owners and their Demographic

Profile

VARIABLES	DF	LEVEL OF SIGNIFICANCE	P-VALUE	INTERPRETATION
AGE	16	.05	.79	NOT SIGNIFICANT
GENDER	4	.05	.29	NOT SIGNIFICANT
YEARS IN BUSINESS	12	.05	.09	NOT SIGNIFICANT

The chi square test of association is used to determine if there exists a significant relationship between the effects of Covid-19 on the marketing strategies of the café restaurant owners and their demographic profile. The test is done on a significance level of .05 and the degrees of freedom are 16, 4, and 12 for the variables age, gender, and years in business respectively. The computed p-values are .79(age), .29(gender), and .09(years in business). These computed values are all greater than .05 level. This indicates the non-existence of a significant relationship between the demographic profile and the perceived effects of Covid-19 on the marketing strategies of the participants. This implies that the owners' perception as to the effects of Covid-19 on their marketing strategies is not influenced by their age, gender, and years in business. Their perception on the effects does not depend on their age, gender, and years in business.

5. SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS, & RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter gives the summary of the study conducted including its salient findings; the conclusions generated from these findings; and the recommendations of the research.

Summary

The thrust of this study was to assess the effects of Covid-19 on the marketing strategies of the café restaurants in San Pedro, Laguna. It specifically sought to find out the demographic characteristics of the owners of these restaurants in terms of age, gender, and years in the business. Aside from the perception of the respondents on these effects, the study also wanted to answer if there is a significant difference in the effects of the pandemic on marketing strategies in terms of product, price, promotion, and place. Further, the study wanted to establish the significance of the relationship that exists between these perceived effects of Covid-19 on the marketing strategies of the restaurant owners and their demographic profile.

The descriptive method of research was used in the study since it wanted to describe a certain situation at the time the study was conducted- the assessment of the café restaurant owners in San Pedro, Laguna on the effects of Covid-19 on their marketing strategies. In addition, the study collected data in order to describe the current status of the subject of the study and to test hypotheses- the significance of the difference of the effects of Covid-19 on marketing strategies in terms of product, price, promotion, and place as well as the relationship of these perceived effects with the participants' demographic profile. The participants of the study were the 30 T owners of café restaurants in San Pedro, Laguna, selected using purposive sampling. The instrument used in gathering the data needed for the study was the survey questionnaire which

was subjected to an internal consistency test using the Cronbach alpha prior to its use. The said test yielded an alpha value of 0.75 interpreted that the instrument was good and therefore acceptable for use. The data collected from the respondents in the survey questionnaire were then analyzed and interpreted using statistical tools appropriate for the problems presented in this research.

The study found out that most of the owners of the café restaurants located in San Pedro, Laguna were young, mostly females, and have been in the food industry for almost 4 to 6 years. The study also found out that as per the assessment made by the owners considered in the study, the Covid-19 pandemic produced a high negative effect on their marketing strategies specifically in the areas of product and price. They saw moderate negative effect in terms of promotion strategies and slight negative effect on place. It has also been determined in the study that the assessments made by the owners significantly differed in the effects of Covid-19 pandemic in the product, pricing, promotional, and place strategies that they implemented at the height of the pandemic. Further, it was also revealed in the study that the assessments made by the owners as to the effects of Covid-19 on their marketing strategies were not influenced by their age, gender, and years in the business.

Conclusions

It is now a fact that the Covid-19 pandemic altered the usual life we had been used to ever since. The effects can be seen in almost every facet of our lives. In this study where the effects of Covid-19 to the marketing strategies of café restaurant owners in San Pedro, Laguna, the following generalizations were arrived at as per the findings of the study:

1. Café restaurants owners in San Pedro, Laguna were young, mostly female, and equipped with adequate skills and knowledge in this line of business given their years in the industry.
2. Covid-19 affected the marketing strategies of these café restaurants adversely. The pandemic brought high negative effects on both the product and pricing strategies of these restaurants. It adversely affected in moderate level the promotional strategies of the restaurant and slightly affected the place strategies implemented by the owners.
3. These effects of Covid-19 on the marketing strategies of the café restaurant owners varied significantly in terms of product, price, promotion, and place. Product and pricing strategies carried the brunt of the pandemic's adverse effects as compared to the effects on promotions and place.
4. The ages, gender, and the years in the business of the restaurant owners were not influential in their perception as to the effects of Covid-19 on their marketing strategies.

Recommendations

In view of the above, the research hereby recommends the following:

1. The owners of the restaurants may formulate contingency plans regarding marketing strategies that are flexible in the event another situation like the pandemic will occur in the future.
2. Management may ensure that the pricing of the products they offer is aligned with the value of the products without reducing its affordability on the part of the consumers.
3. The owners may intensify the use of different social media platforms to the maximum in the promotion of their products considering the power these wield nowadays. In addition, using social media in promotions is inexpensive yet very effective especially during the height of the pandemic.
4. A study may be conducted in the future to look into the factors that cause the differences in the perception as to the effects of the pandemic on the different aspects of marketing strategies particularly the findings herein wherein product and price were the most adversely affected.

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